

IOT ENHANCING THE EFFICIENT OF SENSORS DATA COLLECTION FROM REAL WORLD: AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The current industry era 4.0 dramatically increase productivity of technology through real-time data collection and analysis. It combines the uniqueness of Internet of Things (IoT) with the capabilities of cloud computing to create insights that help optimize the decision-making process. With this excellent technology which provide sensor management system in a cloud server that used for the data collection. Through this method, the data are easily control and manage in anywhere at any place through Information Communication Technology (ICT) devices as a remote. This paper provides a cross review related to IoT.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Sensor Data, Data Collection

INTRODUCTION

According to (Haller et al., 2009; Plageras et al., 2018) the Internet of Things (IoT) has been found in several years. It was first introduced by the MIT Auto-ID Center, a precursor to the current EPC global organization, and at that time stood for the vision of the world in which all physical things were marked with an RFID (Jia et al., 2012) transponder with a unique global ID - EPC or electronic product code. RFID (Yaacob et al., 2013) easily enables tracking of objects and EPCs act as links to data what the Internet can consider about each individual object and through this, the meaning of the Internet of Things has grown. IoT(Ray, 2018) represents a modern approach whereby the boundaries between real and digital domains are being abolished by consistently transforming each physical device into an intelligent alternative available to provide smart services (Atlam et al., 2018). Besides that, using a sensor or series of sensors, the additional information on the objects or environments(Yang et al., 2013) they may have may also be recorded. Because IoT(Gregorio et al., 2020) can be used on billions of devices, it is made up of a large number of sources of

information, which produces large amounts of partially structured or unstructured data which known as Big Data(Sakharkar et al., 2017) and has contain of three characteristics which like the data types, velocity like the data generation frequency and volume like the data size. As mentioned in the (Atlam et al., 2018)

with many predicting that Big Data (Raafat et al., 2017) will reach 50 billion IoT devices by 2020, it is important to pay more attention to the transportation, access, storage and processing of enormous amounts of data that will be generated. Today, with in-depth IoT research and its application, the IoT's attributes(Huacarpuma et al., 2017) to overall information indexing, reliable transfer, and intelligent operation have made it a major means of data acquisition and delivery (Yan-E, 2011). Although, the real-time data analysis and aggregate information from IoT devices(Zanella et al., 2014) opens incredible opportunities to manage and control smart city infrastructure in a more efficient and sustainable way(Bennati and Pournaras, 2018).

METHOD

The systematic literature review of the current and previous studies targeting in the IoT, sensors data related to data collection and others related topics has been conducted in order to get the detailed overview and clarification.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The existing literature review has been done through the parameter which are title, authors, what, where, how, result and weakness or future study.

No.	Title	Authors	What	Where	How	Result	Weakness / Future Study
1.	Efficient IoT-based sensor BIG Data collection– processing and analysis in smart	(Plageras et al., 2018)	The purpose of this is investigating and proposed new method related to collect and manage sensor data in smart building	-	-Used the star and mesh network topologies. - Implemented in a simulation environment of Cooja Contiki	Lead to the energy efficient smart building, and thus in a Green Smart Building	Deep analyze for the Monitoring technology instead focus on the use of

	building s						sensor s, in order to achiev e optima l outco me below the Cloud enviro nment.
2.	How the internet of things technology enhances emergency response operations	(Yang et al., 2013)	This paper introduces IoT technology for use in the emergency management community	-	Task-technology fit (TTF) and technology acceptance model (TAM) approached.	IoT technology meets the needs of the identified information. IoT technology adds value to emergency response operations in terms of efficient collaboration, accurate state awareness, and complete	There are several limitations found in this study. Assumption in detail by incorporating TAM with TTF. potential impact between causal attributes and conse

						resource visibility	quent attributes.
3.	Customized IoT enabled Wireless Sensing and Monitoring Platform for Smart Buildings	(Shah and Mishra, 2016)	This paper is presenting customized Internet of Things (IoT) allows the Wireless Tracking and Monitoring Platform to monitor Temperature, relative humidity and light in the context of building automation	India	Customized hopping method	Average power consumption of the transmitter node is 43.25 mW. Developed android application is tested on a smart phone based on android 4.3.	Further reduction in power is It may be through algorithms, hardware optimization and encoding techniques and depending on the specific application.
4.	The Internet of Things in an Enterprise Context	(Haller et al., 2009)	This paper provides the literature review on how it relates to the future of the Internet as a whole, and where	-	The systematic literature review on the several related topics has been done in detailed.	Finding shown the value of IoT.	Review

			the value of the business lies in making it attractive for companies to invest in it.				
5.	Integration of Cloud Computing with Internet of Things: Challenges and Open Issues	(Atlam et al., 2018)	The objective of this study is to review the issues and challenge related to integration of Cloud with IoT.	-	Performed the systematic literature review related to existing for cloud computing, IoT, big data and others.	Provides an overview of Cloud integration into IoT by highlighting the benefits of integration and implementation challenges detailed been explained.	Several issues have been found related to data such as Managing a large amount of data is an important issue, as the overall performance of the application is highly dependent on the nature of this

							data management service. Finding the perfect data management solution that will enable the Cloud to manage large amounts of data is still a big problem
6.	Design of Intelligent Agriculture Management Information System Based on IoT	(Yan-E, 2011)	Introducing the concept of agricultural information management and analyzing the characteristics of Agriculture data, design methods and architecture	China	Design developed and implement the example system in production.	The purpose of Agriculture Management Information System (AMIS) is to improve the level of agricultur	Enhancing the efficiency of analytics and processes, cloud computing technology has been

			of MIS Smart Agriculture			al informatio n process and enhance the intelligent manage ment and decision of agricultur al productio n.	used, cloud compu ting is web- based proces sing, where shared resour ces, softwa re and informat ion are provid ed for compu ters and other device s (such as smartp hones) upon Interne t reques t. Using a smart cloud compu ter platfor m can ensure
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							that big data of the internet is real-time analysis, processed, controlled and controlled and creates an efficient and reliable decision-making service system for high-level management and large-scale industrial applications.
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7.	Privacy-enhancing aggregation of Internet of Things data via sensors grouping	This paper is focusing on Increased aggregation of privacy of distributed sensor data, such as residential energy use or traffic information.	(Bennati and Pournaras, 2018)	Switzerland	-A grouping mechanism was introduced that improves privacy by sharing aggregate data first at the group level compared to the baseline scenario. - The proposed system and its generic usability are evaluated using real-world data from two smart city pilot projects	Contributing new opportunities to improve the privacy of all of these mechanisms: the adaptation of network organizations as a new way to improve privacy on the Internet of Things. IoT-PGA privacy and accuracy are measured using real-data from two smart city pilot projects to assess general usability	Random grouping
8.	IoT real time data acquisition	(Atmoko et al., 2017)	This study proposes the use of MQTT as a	Indonesia	-By using the temperature and	Improved data quality and	

	on using MQTT protocol		communication protocol, which is one of the data communication protocols for IoT.		humidity sensors due to physical parameters are often required as environmental condition parameters . -Data retrieval is performed in real time and stored in the MySQL database. - Developed the web-based and mobile for online monitoring	reliability using the MQTT protocol	
9.	The real time monitoring of water quality in IoT environment	(Vijayakumar and Ramya, 2015)	This study presents the low cost system design and development for real-time monitoring of water quality in IoT	India	- Parameters such as temperature, PH, turbidity, conductivity, dissolved oxygen was measured. - The measured	The proposed system consists of several water quality parameters, a Raspberry Pi B + core controller and an IoT	Future work: Implement water biological parameters and install systems in several

					<p>value of the sensor can be processed by the core controller. The PI B raspberry model can be used as a core controller</p>	<p>module (USR WIFI 232). -Devices are low cost, more efficient and capable of processing, analyzing, transmitting and viewing data in the cloud and even via WIFI to mobile devices. These can be implemented in accordance with environmental monitoring, ecosystem monitoring, etc. and data can be found anywhere</p>	<p>l pool locations as well as in water distribution networks to collect water quality data and transmit it to water boards</p>
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						in the world.	
10.	Fog Intelligence for Real-Time IoT Sensor Data Analytics	(Raafat et al., 2017)	This study is presents a new approach for novelty detection in sensor signals	Kuwait	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Homoscedasticity and statistical features extraction -Extract the important events in sensor data in real time when used with neural classifiers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Tested on four different types of sensors (light, temperature, CO2 and humidity) for resident detection. -For light sensors, the detection accuracy of the appliances reached 98.44% while both sensitivity and accuracy reached 96.49% and 100.00% on set1 testing for occupancy detection. -The performance indicators 	Future research will focus on adding more features to improve system reliability in an uncontrolled environment.

						demonstrate the effectiveness of extracted features for detecting novelty in sensor signals	
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CONCLUSION

As Internet of Things (IoT) is a concept aimed to extending the benefits of continuous internet extensions for things like data sharing, remote control and data monitoring. Existing findings founds that IoT has been implemented in several

Studies for monitor and manage the data which still need to continue the further research in order to enhance the sensor related to real data.

REFERENCES

- Atlam, H.F., Alenezi, A., Alharthi, A., Walters, R.J., and Wills, G.B., 2018. Integration of cloud computing with internet of things: Challenges and open issues. In: *Proceedings - 2017 IEEE International Conference on Internet of Things, IEEE Green Computing and Communications, IEEE Cyber, Physical and Social Computing, IEEE Smart Data, iThings-GreenCom-CPSCom-SmartData 2017*.
- Atmoko, R.A., Riantini, R., and Hasin, M.K., 2017. IoT real time data acquisition using MQTT protocol. In: *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*.
- Bennati, S. and Pournaras, E., 2018. Privacy-enhancing aggregation of Internet of Things data via sensors grouping. *Sustainable Cities and Society*.
- Gregorio, F., González, G., Schmidt, C., and Cousseau, J., 2020. Internet of Things. In: *Signals and Communication Technology*.
- Haller, S., Karnouskos, S., and Schroth, C., 2009. The Internet of things in an enterprise context. In: *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*.
- Huacarpuma, R.C., De Sousa Junior, R.T., De Holanda, M.T., Albuquerque, R. de O., Villalba, L.J.G., and Kim, T.H., 2017. Distributed data service for data management in internet of things middleware. *Sensors (Switzerland)*.

- Jia, X., Feng, Q., Fan, T., and Lei, Q., 2012. RFID technology and its applications in Internet of Things (IoT). In: *2012 2nd International Conference on Consumer Electronics, Communications and Networks, CECNet 2012 - Proceedings*.
- Plageras, A.P., Psannis, K.E., Stergiou, C., Wang, H., and Gupta, B.B., 2018. Efficient IoT-based sensor BIG Data collection–processing and analysis in smart buildings. *Future Generation Computer Systems*.
- Raafat, H.M., Hossain, M.S., Essa, E., Elmougy, S., Tolba, A.S., Muhammad, G., and Ghoneim, A., 2017. Fog Intelligence for Real-Time IoT Sensor Data Analytics. *IEEE Access*.
- Ray, P.P., 2018. A survey on Internet of Things architectures. *Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences*.
- Sakharkar, V.S., Dande, M., and Mate, S., 2017. Cloud and Big Data : A Compelling Combination. *IJESC*, 7 (3), pp.4867–4870.
- Shah, J. and Mishra, B., 2016. Customized IoT Enabled Wireless Sensing and Monitoring Platform for Smart Buildings. *Procedia Technology*.
- Vijayakumar, N. and Ramya, R., 2015. The real time monitoring of water quality in IoT environment. In: *ICIIECS 2015 - 2015 IEEE International Conference on Innovations in Information, Embedded and Communication Systems*.
- Yaacob, N.M., Ghani, M.K.A., and Basari, A.S.H., 2013. A Framework for Accessing Patient Health Records Through Multi Channel of Devices. In: *e-Proceeding of Software Engineering Postgraduates Workshop (SEPoW)*. pp.31.
- Yan-E, D., 2011. Design of intelligent agriculture management information system based on IoT. In: *Proceedings - 4th International Conference on Intelligent Computation Technology and Automation, ICICTA 2011*.
- Yang, L., Yang, S.H., and Plotnick, L., 2013. How the internet of things technology enhances emergency response operations. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*.
- Zanella, A., Bui, N., Castellani, A., Vangelista, L., and Zorzi, M., 2014. Internet of things for smart cities. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*.